

Memorandum in response to the proposed bill ‘The Promotion of Proper Human Sexual
Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill 2021’
By

We are ALL Ghana Coalition

SEPTEMBER 2021

MEMORANDUM

TO: The Honourable Chairman and Members
Committee on Constitutional, Legal and Parliamentary Affairs

FROM: We are All Ghana Coalition

SUBJECT: Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021

DATE: September 30, 2021

CC: Office of the Attorney-General

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1 Introduction

Following the notice dated September 15, 2021, the Parliamentary Service, on behalf of the Parliamentary Select Committee on Constitutional, Legal and Parliamentary Affairs, issued a request for written memoranda on the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian

Family Values Bill, 2021 (“the Bill”). We humbly submit this Memorandum in response to this request.

We Are All Ghana is a campaign to stop the passing of anti- lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer (or questioning), intersex, and asexual (“LGBT+”) legislation in Ghana and to create a permanent coalition of those seeking justice, equality and human rights for all.

We are grateful to your Committee for the opportunity to submit this memorandum. This Memorandum seeks to assist the Committee in its review and consideration of the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021.

The United Nations definition of human rights below, “Human rights are rights inherent to all human beings, regardless of race, sex, nationality, ethnicity, language, religion, or any other status. Human rights include the right to life and liberty, freedom from slavery and torture, freedom of opinion and expression, the right to work and education, and many more. Everyone is entitled to these rights, without discrimination”. The proposed Bill pursues a course of action which seeks to deny the universally accepted definition of human rights for groups of people who identify as members and allies of the LGBTQI+ community in the Federal Republic of Ghana. It is for these reasons that we stand in firm opposition to the Bill.

2 The Law

2.1 The Protection of Ghanaian Family Values

We, the members of the We Are ALL Ghana Coalition (the “Ghana Coalition”), firmly believe that the 1992 Constitution of Ghana is clear: every “person” is free and entitled to equal protection under the law, including the freedom to form the family of their choosing! The

proposed Bill is therefore, a priori, unconstitutional insofar as it criminalizes the very personhood of several Ghanaians. Unless there is respect for the right to privacy and safety in the home of each Ghanaian, there can be no freedom and justice in our land.

As such, we believe that Government has no role in the bedrooms of consenting adults. Neither do children. Without safe, well educated and happy children, raised in the best of Ghanaian culture, there will be no enduring Ghana. Thus, we endorse Article 28(1)(e) of the Constitution which enjoins Parliament “to enact laws necessary to ensure that the protection and advancement of the family as the unit of society are safeguarded in promotion of the interest of children.”

Please note that “the family” is appropriately left undefined under Ghana’s Constitution, as ours is a land that respects different kinds of family units, various religions, cultures, and systems of belief. Consequently, each adult is, and must be, free to create a family of their own choosing. The Bill, however, denies that family forming freedom to all too many Ghanaians. It unnecessarily opens the nation’s bedrooms to inspection and approval by our neighbors and the State. Surely, the Constitution that protects both polygamy and monogamy necessarily protects all other forms of family created by consenting adults.

Finally, we stand by the freedom of religious and cultural institutions to guide the mores of behavior of their adherents and members. But, they cannot and must not dictate to the nation as a whole. Just as no church is required by law to perform a polygamous marriage, neither should any religious institution be required by law to perform a LGBT+ marriage. This means that any religious or cultural institution, let alone any member of Parliament, can be firmly opposed to LGBT+ marriage, and yet still affirm as a matter of fundamental freedom and justice the right of

every Ghanaian to choose their own religion, their work, and the family they form. For these reasons, it is our view that the Bill should be defeated.

2.2 Legal Analysis

The legal analysis of the Bill commences with a brief outline of certain provisions of the Constitution. Article 17 of the Constitution enshrines the equality of all persons under law and each person's freedom from discrimination. Article 17 states:

“(1) All persons shall be equal before the law.

(2) A person shall not be discriminated against on grounds of gender, race, colour, ethnic origin, religion, creed, or social or economic status.

(3) For the purpose of this article, “discriminate” means to give different treatment to different persons attributable only or mainly to their respective descriptions by race, place of origin, political opinions, colour, gender, occupation, religion or creed, whereby persons of one description are subjected to disabilities or restrictions to which persons of another description are not made subject or are granted privileges or advantages which are not granted to persons of another description.

(4)(b) Nothing in this article shall prevent Parliament from enacting laws that are reasonably necessary to provide for matters relating to adoption, marriage, divorce, burial, devolution of property on death or other matters of personal law;

(5) Nothing shall be taken to be inconsistent with this article which is allowed to be done under any provision of this Chapter.”

Although the Bill purports to be a Parliamentary law required under Article 28(1), qualifying for the shield against constitutional scrutiny of Article 17(5), a careful review shows that it runs

afoul of Article 17(2). In the first place, the term “gender” as used in the Constitution is synonymous with the term “sex” as used in the 1979 Constitution. Therefore, discrimination on the ground of sex is prohibited under the Constitution. Paragraph 161 of the Report of the Committee of Experts (Constitution) on Proposals for a Draft Constitution of Ghana (1991) (hereinafter referred to as the “Report”) that preceded the Constitution stated: “During its discussions, the Committee considered Article 31 of the 1979 Constitution and recommends that wherever the word “sex” appears in any of the clauses it should be replaced by the word “gender”. The Committee proposes that all persons should be equal before the law. It further proposes that no person may be discriminated against on the grounds of gender, race, colour, ethnic origin, religion, creed or social or economic status.” Self-evidently, the term “sex” as a synonym for “gender” includes “the two main categories into which humans and most other living things are divided on the basis of their reproductive functions.” But, it cannot be limited to those two categories. If, for example, an intersex person was born in Ghana, that person would be guaranteed protection against discrimination under article 17(2) of the Constitution. That such an individual would be rare and a member of an infinitesimally small minority would have no bearing on their right to equal treatment under the law and freedom from state sponsored intervention. In similar vein, the scientific developments that enable a person’s sex or gender status to be changed in the course of a person’s life, rather than at the time of birth, cannot deprive that person of their right to equal treatment either. Indeed, the Bill’s inclusion of such a restrictive definition of “gender” (i.e. “gender” means the binary sex categories of male and female assigned at birth, and the behavioural, cultural and psychological traits typically associated with either sex, but does not include transgender, gender non-conformity or non-binary categories”) demonstrates that, in the

absence of this restrictive definition, the default definition of “gender” would encompass the very categories that the Bill seeks to excise. Moreover, this Bill cannot be viewed as “necessary” to “the promotion of the interest of children” since it fails to provide any scientific or statistical evidence showing a connection between evolving gender classifications and the welfare of Ghanaian children.

There is also a cultural framework which should be borne in mind. The Bill, as well as its explanatory memorandum, asserts that homosexuality is a taboo under Ghana’s different traditional cultures. Assuming, solely for the purpose of argument, that the taboo pronouncements are accurate, it ignores the question whether all taboos attach criminal sanction to the prohibited conduct under customary laws. For example, the Ten Commandments prohibits adultery, murder, theft, envy, and lust. Only murder and theft among those taboos constitute criminal offences under Ghana’s Criminal Offences Act. Rattray’s Ashanti Law and Constitution, published in 1929, contains extensive discussion about the treatment of adultery under Ashanti law. In several cases, the punishment for adultery is damages. (It is noteworthy that RS Rattray’s treatise on Ashanti Law and Constitution pays scant regard to sodomy. John Mensah Sarbah’s book on Fanti Customary Law also pays much more attention to adultery than to sodomy.) With all due respect to the National House of Chiefs, a person who is a member of one of the categories enumerated in Clause 1 of the Bill does not seem to have the status of a criminal under traditional Akan law. In fact, kindly note that the Nzemas, as just one example, have a form of marriage between two men known as Friendship Marriage. In sum, neither tradition nor religious doctrine justify elevating homosexuality to the status of a criminal offence.

It is time to turn to the actual language of the Bill. In simple terms, the Bill violates the freedom of speech, the freedom of assembly, among other constitutional violations. At the outset, the words of Justice Charles Hayfron-Benjamin ring loud and clear. He stated in the 1993 case of *New Patriotic Party vs. the Inspector-General of Police* that lesbians and gays had rights of assembly or protests under the Constitution.

Secondly, the definition of “proper human sexual rights” of a person in Clause 2 of the Bill is vague. It provides that a person has a right to “physical, emotional, and psychological well being and enhancement”. This right belongs, ostensibly, to only individuals who are recognized as male and female at birth. It discriminates against all other types of persons, thus violating the right to equal treatment of those other types of persons.

Next, the definition of Ghanaian family values appears to be restrictive insofar as it contemplates monogamy. Yet, polygamy is legal in Ghana. Clause 2 states that “respect for marriage as a lifelong relationship between man and a woman, each of whose gender is assigned at birth”. Equal treatment under the experience of Ghanaians suggests that the definition of marriage should be expanded.

Clause 3.1 imposes a duty on all Ghanaian citizens to promote proper human sexual rights and Ghanaian family values. How this duty is to be enforced or measured is not explained.

Clause 4.1(a) prohibits a person from undermining the proper human sexual rights and Ghanaian family values. “Undermining” is an undefined term in the Bill. The exact meaning of this

prohibition is vague and ambiguous. The penalty for a violation of this Clause is a minimum term of two months and a maximum term of four months.

Clause 5.1 obliges a person who sees the commission of an offence under clause 2 of this Bill to report the commission of the offence to a police officer or some other office holder. It seeks to turn all members of the community into active informers as well as individuals who may observe some of the practices enumerated in Clause 2.

Clause 6.1 purports to criminalize several acts deemed to be practiced typically by members of the LGBT+ community. Yet, by virtue of Clause 6.3(a) and Clause 6.3(b), the acts do not seem to constitute criminal offences when performed by a heterosexual. The criminal penalties attached to conduct described in clause 6.3(a) and clause 6.3(b) for LGBT+ community members that do not apply to other groups of people is in direct conflict with Article 17 of the Constitution because it discriminates against a group based on its sex or sexual orientation.

Clause 10.(1) and 2(a), together, are unconstitutional because they prohibit actions taken by the LGBT community members, when such actions are permissible by heterosexuals. Again, discrimination is being committed by the state.

Clauses 12, 13, 14, 15, and 16 violate freedom of speech and assembly.

2.3 Way Forward

The way forward is for the Bill to be withdrawn or defeated in its entirety. Alternatively, Parliament may wish to seek a legal opinion from the Attorney-General on the constitutionality (or otherwise) of the Bill. Simultaneously with this Bill, a legal action should be brought before the Supreme Court testing the constitutionality of the sodomy provisions in the Criminal Offences Act, along with an action for a declaratory order that the Bill, in its current form, is unconstitutional.

3 Customs

The bill describes a unanimous rejection of gender and sexual diversity among various ethnic groups, but fails to cite peer reviewed citations that verify the accuracy of those claims. Likewise, it obscures the role British and Arab imperialism has played, through law, in shaping contemporary attitudes towards Ghanaian citizens across the gender and sexual spectrum. For example, anti-homosexual legislature was first introduced in the country during British colonial rule in Ghana, formerly the Gold Coast, in the 1860s which implies that gender and sexual diversity was salient enough to warrant legislation by British colonizers. Similarly, former British colonies such as Ghana are 22 times more likely to have laws that criminalize Ghanaians on the basis of their sexuality (O'Mahoney 2014). Thus, state sanctioned legislation that excludes and denigrates Ghanaian citizens on the basis of immutable characteristics such as gender identity and sexuality should be recognized as entrenching colonial hierarchies that denigrate other Ghanaians. Such legislation is rooted in British Victorian ideals that are not indigenous to what is now known as Ghana.

Furthermore, considering that Africa, which includes Ghana, is the home of genetic, linguistic, and rich cultural diversity, it should be no surprise that such diversity includes gender and sexual diversity too. Many of our ancestors affirmed human diversity as something to be understood not

demonized. To illustrate, the adinkra symbol Funtumfunefu Denkyemfunefu shows two conjoined crocodiles which normally being independent creatures, are forced to work together and unite in order to survive. Funtumfunefu Denkyemfunefu evokes the interconnected nature of all Ghanaians which includes LGBTQ Ghanaians who are our mothers, fathers, sisters, brothers, spiritual advisers, doctors, lawyers, and other essential and cherished members of our community. Their safety and flourishing is interconnected with ours. Similarly, many of our ancestors recognized the ongoing need to understand the mysteries of life which are best embodied in adinkra symbols such as nea onim which articulates the ongoing quest for knowledge and denkyem meaning adaptability. However, this law criminalizes sympathy and dissent, all of which would rob Ghanaians of the opportunity to engage in thoughtful discussion about gender and sexuality in light of science, a rich cultural heritage of inclusion and diversity, and rigorous theological discussion by respected and thoughtful Christian and Islamic scholars who affirm the dignity, respect and protection of LGBT+ persons.

4 International Obligations

4.1 Human Rights Treaties

Ghana has signed and ratified several regional and international human rights treaties that oblige it to respect and protect the rights of LGBT+ people, albeit not explicit, including the right to equality before the law, non-discrimination, human dignity, privacy and the right to be free from violence. These include the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (African Charter), the Protocol to the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights on the Rights of Women in Africa (Maputo Protocol), the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination

against Women (CEDAW) and the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR).

4.2 Ghana's Obligations under International Law

By becoming a party to these treaties Ghana has accepted legal obligations to exercise due diligence in protecting people from all forms of violence regardless of their sexual orientation or gender identity, whether perpetrated by state or non-state actors.

Under Article 4(2) of the Maputo Protocol states are required to take necessary measures to enact and enforce laws to prohibit and punish all forms of violence against women. In October 2012, the African Commission adopted its General Comment to article 14(1)(d) and (e) of the Maputo Protocol, in which it expressly included sexual orientation as a recognized ground of discrimination.

Resolution 275 underscores the obligation on African states to act with due diligence to protect LGBT+ individuals from all forms of violence. Ghana referenced Resolution 275 at the UN Human Rights Council in June 2016 when abstaining from a vote on the appointment of a United Nations Independent Expert on protection against violence and discrimination based on sexual orientation and gender identity. The Ghanaian delegate explained why Ghana had taken a relatively "progressive" position in abstaining from the vote, rather than following the lead of other African states that voted against the resolution.

5 SDGs

The SDGs are the result of the most consultative and inclusive process in the history of the United Nations. Grounded in international human rights law, the agenda offers critical

opportunities to further advance the realization of human rights for all people everywhere, without discrimination.

Transformative: As an agenda for “people, planet, prosperity, peace and partnership”, the 2030 Agenda offers a paradigm shift from the traditional model of development. It provides a transformative vision for people and planet-centred, human rights-based, and gender-sensitive sustainable development that goes far beyond the narrow vision of the MDGs.

Comprehensive: Alongside a wide range of social, economic and environmental objectives, the 2030 Agenda promises “more peaceful, just and inclusive societies which are free from fear and violence” with attention to democratic governance, rule of law, access to justice and personal security (in Goal 16), as well as an enabling international environment (in Goal 17 and throughout the framework). It therefore covers issues related to all human rights, including economic, civil, cultural, political, social rights and the right to development.

Inclusive: The new Agenda strives to leave no-one behind, envisaging “a world of universal respect for equality and non-discrimination” between and within countries, including gender equality, by reaffirming the responsibilities of all States to “respect, protect and promote human rights, without distinction of any kind as to race, colour, sex, language, religion, political or other opinions, national and social origin, property, birth, disability or other status.

6 Business

The bill undermines outreach initiatives taken by the Ghanaian government to members of the African diaspora as it legitimizes state sanctioned discrimination which will erode Ghana's reputation as a beacon of human rights. Peter Tatchell's *The Economic Cost of Homophobia*, describes the economic consequences of anti-LGBT+ legislation. For example, “countries that

criminalise homosexuality are jeopardising their share of an LGBT+ travel market estimated to be worth US\$211 billion per annum". Moreover, this Bill will create brain drain as educated, skilled LGBT and non-LGBT Ghanians leave Ghana for nations on the continent and international community that affirm human diversity and inclusion.

We believe that the Bill will seriously undermine Ghana's aspiration to be an economic, social and political leader on the continent and world stage.

7 Summary

Article 1 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights by the United Nations, a body to which the Republic of Ghana belongs states that, "all human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights. They are endowed with reason and conscience and would act towards one another in a spirit of brotherhood". Passing a bill to police the sexuality and consensual sexual expressions of citizens of the Republic takes away their sovereignty, dehumanizing them in ways that violates Article 5: "no one shall be subjected to torture or to cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment" which has been proposed in this Bill as conversion therapy.

Moreover, the proposed Bill asserts that "LGBTQI+ activities threaten the concept of family and the associated value systems that are central to the social structure of all ethnic groups in Ghana". The word "activities" used here is at a minimum unduly vague, and at worst, refers to activity that is criminalized solely with respect to members of the LGBTQI+ community.

The Bill also states, "the concept of family for Ghanaians has always been of society-initiated marriage between a man and a woman whose genders are assigned at birth." It is however not uncommon to have persons born intersex, with both male and female biological characteristics. (It is also not uncommon to have nuclear families that are not "society initiated".) The Bill's

claim of proper family virtues being the sole preserve of marriage between female and male automatically and unnecessarily ostracizes persons who were born intersex. We argue that a person cannot be criminally punished for their biological make up or for their unique attributes per se. Chapter 5 of the 1992 Constitution states: "Every person in Ghana, whatever his race, place of origin, political opinion, colour, religion, creed or gender shall be entitled to the fundamental human rights and freedoms of the individual contained in this Chapter but subject to respect for the rights and freedoms of others and for the public interest." Furthermore, 17(1) provides that all persons shall be equal before the law; 21(1)(a) guarantees freedom of speech and expression, which shall include freedom of the press and other media and (d) freedom of assembly, including the freedom to take part in processions and demonstration; 21(1)(e) promises the freedom of association, which shall include freedom to form or join trade unions or other association, national and international, for the protection of their interest. (By invading the LGBTQI+ community center, the government of Ghana violated Chapter 5, article 20(1). The parliament will argue 20(1)(a) in defense of this violation; however, the safe space that was shut down had not per se hindered public safety, order, morality, health or town and country planning.)

If the Bill is bold enough to assert that the Constitution of the great Republic of Ghana is not absolute, will the bill be calling the minds that put the documents together incapable or will this proposed bill be hinting towards a reformation or an amendment of the constitution of the Republic? The bill mentions the need for a separation of prohibited acts from the right to engage in their advocacy. It goes further to state the prohibited acts are injurious to public health and safety thus any groups, organizations, or meetings to promote these prohibited acts will by extension be unlawful. Prohibited act here is defined as "unnatural carnal knowledge" within

which the LGBTQI+ community were not listed. The phrase carnal knowledge is a rather archaic word for sexual intercourse and sexual intercourse is not limited to vaginal penetration with a penis. Sexual intercourse or in this case “carnal knowledge” is knowledge to be left for the consenting persons in its engagement. I argue the reference to *Banosin v. The Republic*; No. J3/2/2014 dated 8th march 2014 has no grounding with this bill because it was a case of the rape of a minor. “It is the female sex organs called the vulva and vagina that are normally penetrated into during any sexual act which can qualify to be carnal knowledge under sections 98 and 99 of Act 29” The key word here is CAN. The statement did not definitively say the penetration of the vagina IS the absolute definition of carnal knowledge. The definition of sexual intercourse varies from person to person and while some form of penetration or insertion is needed for procreation, it would be quite backwards for the esteemed Republic of Ghana to assume that is the only function of sexual intercourse. The average Ghanaian family having less children than generations before is testament to the fact that sexual intercourse serves more than the need for procreation. It is a form of pleasure to be consensually enjoyed by adults. The bill states that according to the 4th National HIV and AIDS Research Conference in Accra, 18.1% of people living with AIDS are gay men. That leaves 81.9% of people in Ghana living with AIDS who are NOT gay men. I believe astute attention to proper sex education with our youth which is not rooted in shame and guilt of natural biological changes which make them more susceptible to sexual explorations, as well as provision of support to at risk persons who utilize sex work as a means of survival might be a better way to combat AIDS. Article 39, Clause (1) and (2)

1) Subject to clause (2) of this article, the State shall take steps to encourage the integration of appropriate customary values into the fabric of national life through formal and informal

education and the conscious introduction of cultural dimensions to relevant aspects of national planning.

2)The State shall ensure that appropriate customary and cultural values are adapted and developed as an integral part of the growing needs of the society as a whole; and in particular that traditional practices which are injurious to the health and well-being of the person are abolished. The bill assumes the above clauses lend themselves to marriage between male and female, automatically “othering” intersex individuals. This bill claims it seeks to strengthen the laws of the republic instead the enactment of this bill will create a separation, animosity, and division between the citizens of the republic. Ghana has earned a reputation for its maintenance of peace since acquiring independence, there is no telling what a bill of this stature could do to this peaceful foundation all Ghanaians have contributed to. The bill itself states that there is NO LEGISLATION that specifically criminalized advocacy for, funding of, promotion of or encouragement of LGBTQI+ activities except the “preparation for committing certain criminal offences, abetment of a criminal offence and conspiracy. The bill assumes a gap in the law creates opportunities for advocates of the LGBTQI+ community to sponsor, promote or proliferate “those” sexual activities but it does not define what sexual activities those are, rendering that argument baseless. The bill mentions promised travel opportunities, allowances, and other gifts as incentives for persons to engage in LGBTQI+ activities (which again it does not clarify). Providing incentives in exchange for sexual favours hold no discrimination towards any sexual orientations. Thus, CONSENSUAL sexual engagements between adults IS not illegal. The degree to which two consenting adults choose to express themselves sexually cannot, by law, be policed by the state especially if those consenting adults are not reporting any harm experienced. The bill argues for its alignment with the United Nations SDG’s 3, 5 and 10. SDG 3

which is to “ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages” has no bearing with consensual sexual interactions of the people of the republic. If the parliament seeks to promote this SDG especially around sexual health and awareness, it could work on implementing a more robust sexual education, awareness, and resource centers to educate the republic and reduce the stigma around sex, sexuality, and sexual health overall. SDG 5 which is “to achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls”, has nothing to do with this bill. Women and girls have been historically underrepresented, sidelined, silenced and their contributions have been unrecognized. Thus, this SDG is in place to prioritize the avenues and resources that will provide visibility to our women and girls to enable them to thrive within structures that have historically been patriarchal. SDG 10 which is to “reduce inequality within and among countries” puts the bill in a chokehold because its very nature propagates the very inequalities the SDG seeks to reduce. There are many things that are humanely, ethically, and morally questionable with this proposed bill, however, below are consequences of the proposed bill according to some its clauses:

1. Clause 1 & 2 applies to persons who identify as lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, transsexual, queer (which is an all-encompassing term), an ally (which extends to heterosexuals as well), pansexual or any other person of contrary “sociocultural” notions of male and female or the relationship between male and female relationship, a person born intersex, persons who support the LGBTQI+ community (who will be termed as an ally) and even some medical practitioners. The arm of this statement extends beyond a scope any citizen of the Republic of Ghana could comprehend and shadows over all citizens of the Republic of Ghana.
2. Clause 4 prohibits a person from engaging in acts that undermine the proper human sexual rights and Ghanaian family values provided for in the bill. Carnal knowledge or sexual

intercourse is an act that occurs within the privacy of consenting adults thus a ban or measure of what is natural or unnatural between consenting human adults seems rather peculiar. In easy words, this bill proposes to rid the Ghanaian adults from pleasures accrued from sexual activities like oral sex and foreplay since they do not involve the penetration of the penis into the vagina.

3. Clause 5 compels citizens of the republic to whistle blow on persons of the LGBTQI+ community. It is important to remember that before we are anything else religiously, biologically, ethnically, nationally, sexually_ we are human first. This clause sets citizens of Ghana up to plant seeds of hatred among themselves which could result in the shifting of the national stability we have enjoyed this far.

4. Clause 10 prohibits gross indecency subjecting persons engaged in this to a fine. The concept of gross indecency is relative and it's unsettling to assume what might be considered decent according to one's values will be the same for another. It is assuming all citizens of the republic must express themselves the same way.

5. Clause 12 to 16 infringes on the freedom of expression and media by banning the use of media, technological platforms, technological accounts, or any other means, produces, procures, markets, broadcast, disseminates, publishes or materials to promoting the LGBTQI+ community and subjects' violators of this to no less than 5 years' jail time.

6. Clause 15 infringes on the right to organize.

7. Clauses 19 to 23 anthropologically "others" members of the LGBTQI+ community by dehumanizing members of the community. Yet the cost of its proposed interventions of "love and care" are to be borne by the very members of the community while simultaneously wanting to prescribe jail time?

The proposed bill apart from its gross dehumanization contradicts itself proving it a baseless argument to discriminate against law abiding citizens of the country on subjective paradigms. An example is seen with the bill encouraging citizens of Ghana to report members or suspected members of the LGBTQI+ community to authorities while discouraging assault, abuse, or harassment whether verbal or physical. Verbal abuse is a type of psychological abuse that involves the use of oral, gestured, and written language directed to a victim. Boltz M, Hoffman D (2017). Abuse is rarely predictable thus the ascribed "vulnerabilities" of members of the LGBTQI+ communities by this bill makes them easy targets for personal and institutionally backed banter and abuse rendering them truly vulnerable.

8 Proposed Interventions

Proposed Interventions: The United Nations, an organization to which the Federal Republic of Ghana belongs agrees that the proposed bill is "are a textbook example of discrimination."

Therefore, below are some proposed interventions:

1. A vote against the bill rendering ineffective immediately
2. Access to inclusive proper sexual and reproductive health centers
3. Noninterference with the operations of the LGBT+ Ghana operations of its community center
4. Open dialogue between parliament, sexual and reproductive health professional and the LGBTQI+ community
5. Arrest and detention of persons who physically or verbally abuse and assault members of the LGBTQI+ community as that constitutes a hate crime

6. General respect for the constitutional rights and freedoms of members of the LGBTQI+ community as citizens of the Republic of Ghana.

9 Conclusion

Before we are anything else, we are human first. Dehumanizing members of the LGBTQI+ community in Ghana is no different than the dehumanizing of people of color during colonization through slavery and other inhumane circumstances. The “Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill” proposed a system of discrimination which regresses the efforts our federal republic has attained since its independence from colonial rule. It is important that in the spirit of unity, we mobilize our full capacity and strength to push our motherland towards the progress we want to see. Every citizen counts. Every life matters. Every contribution, invaluable.

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